

Doctoral Research in Assamese Language and Literature A Bibliometric Analysis of Theses Uploaded in Shodhganga

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Abstract

The present study is a bibliometric analysis of 445 theses in the domain of 'Assamese Language and Literature' for which Doctoral Degree was awarded from the Universities in Assam and have been uploaded in the Shodhganga, the repository of Indian theses. Out of 19 universities in Assam, 12 have signed memorandum of understanding (MoU) with Shodhganga to upload their theses and dissertations to this repository. It is observed that as on the date of carrying out the data collection for study, a total of 9397 Doctoral theses have been uploaded by the Universities in North East India. Of these, the share of theses on Assamese Language and Literature, comes to 4.74% (445 numbers), This study attempts to analyse parameters such as year of awarding Ph D to the theses, year of uploading the electronic version to the Shodhganga repository, university-wise share, name of supervising guide, number of references attached and total number of pages. Only four universities, namely Gauhati University, Dibrugarh University, Mahapurusha Srimanta Sankaradeva Viswavidyalaya and the Bodoland University are found to have uploaded ETDs in Assamese Language and Literature. Gauhati University is seen to have the major share of 87.41% of the total. The two year period 2017 – 2018 has been identified as most productive in the sense 100 Ph Ds were awarded by two universities – Gauhati University and Dibrugarh University – on this subject domain. Gauhati University has uploaded 389 (87.41%) theses and it is followed by Dibrugarh University with 46 (10.33%) theses. Dr. Umesh Deka of Gauhati University is identified as the Research Supervisor to guide the highest number (24) of theses. The second position goes to Dr. Dipti Phukan Patgiri of the same university. The number of references attached to the theses is in the range of 36 to 450 and the average number comes to 135 per thesis. Theses from Dibrugarh University have the highest average number (160) of references.

Keywords: Doctoral theses; Assamese language; Universities of Assam; Bibliometrics; Shodhganga.

1. Introduction

Electronic theses and dissertations (ETDs) are invaluable resources for advanced study and research in any domain of knowledge. No institution engaged in higher education and research can underestimate the value of previous research publications as the foundation on which

further research has to proceed. Earlier, research papers and theses emanating from an institution were considered as private and copyrighted property of the institution, and therefore were of restricted access and that too with the permission of the authorities. But today,

consequent to the Open Access movement, the scenario has been changed. Research papers and theses produced as outcome of research carried out utilising public money are viewed as public property and therefore bound to be made accessible to the public without any restriction. As a result, universities and research institutions have started to create and maintain open-access digital repository/ institutional repository of their research contributions. Such open access institutional repositories ensure visibility of the respective institutions at a global level and serve as a means that justify their existence.

Shodhganga is a digital repository of Indian ETDs setup by the INFLIBNET Centre, an autonomous Inter-University Centre (IUC) of the University Grants Commission, started with the objective of promoting and establishing communication facilities to improve capability in information transfer and access, that provide support to scholarship, learning, research and academic pursuit through cooperation and involvement of agencies concerned. Shodhganga provides a platform for research students to upload their full-text of Ph.D. theses and make it available to the academic community as well as the public in open access. The repository can capture, index, store, disseminate and preserve the ETDs submitted by the researchers. Shodhganga replicates the academic structure of each university in terms of departments and centers, and colleges of each university must facilitate ease of navigation. Currently, 665 universities have signed the Memorandum of Understanding (MoU) with the INFLIBNET, and a total of 395,514 dissertations have been submitted.

2. Review of Literature

Jhamb & Samim (2017) have made a study of the contributions made by central universities in India to the Shodhganga. Their observation is that, as on the date of their study, out of the 46 central universities in India, only 27 have been sharing their research results with Shodhganga or signed an MoU with it. Science departments have a leading position in respect of contribution to Shodhganga. The study by Gogoi (2018) is a bibliometric analysis of 548 Ph.D. theses in LIS

produced by the Indian universities during 2013-2017, using Shodhganga as the source of data. Factors considered for analysis are year-wise productivity, university-wise, and state-wise contributions. Subject-wise and guide-wise analysis is also included.

Mohamed & Divya (2018) made an explorative study of the potential of electronic thesis repositories and their feasibility among Indian scholastic and research groups. According to them, with the explosive growth of the Internet, many ETD repositories are accessible worldwide. Through open-access archives, some elite research institutes, such as the Indian Institute of Science, have started providing access to their ETDs. Vidyanidhi, the INDEST Consortium, CSIR, and the INFLIBNET Center are working on implementing an open-access ETD bibliographic database. Their work further explored the collections, software used, and ETD policy frameworks of various academic and scientific institutions in India. They highlight the major merit of Open repositories of ETDs as playing a vital role in the academic community because it helps prevent duplication of research that has already been done.

Khode (2020) has carried out a study to examine the status of contributions made by universities in Madhya Pradesh to the Shodhganga open-access repository. Out of 59 universities in the state, 29 have signed an MoU with Shodhganga to contribute their ETDs; but only 20 have been uploading their theses. Dr. Harisingh Gour Vishwavidyalaya, Sagar has uploaded the highest number of 1847 (37.23%) theses. Biological Sciences, Chemical Sciences and Management account for 16.4%, 11.9% and 10.6% respectively of the total number of ETDs uploaded. Verma et al (2020) conducted a study of the doctoral theses and dissertations in Library and Information Science submitted in the central universities of North-East India uploaded on the Shodhganga portal. A total of 67 Ph.D. theses uploaded by the universities to the portal were analyzed based on various parameters. The highest number of theses were submitted in 2015, the highest number of Ph.Ds were awarded in

2013. The number of pages of theses is in the range of 151-200 pages, and Prof. Pravakar Rath was identified as the most productive supervisor with 8 Ph Ds under his guideship. Another quantitative study of the theses in LIS was carried out by Simte & Phuritsabam (2021). The study covers 100 doctoral theses in LIS awarded by four central universities in the Northeast Region of India from 1989-2018. The study showed that there is a steady growth of research activity in the discipline, as indicated by the gradual increase in the production of doctoral theses by the research community in the region. Research is conducted on a variety of traditional and modern topics of library science.

Saloi (2021) made another study to evaluate the contribution made by central universities in North East India to the Shodhganga repository. Out of the total 10 central universities in North East India, 9 universities have signed the Shodhganga repository MoU, and all contributed their theses and dissertations for this project. North Eastern Hill University (NEHU) made the first initiative to sign an MoU with Shodhganga and has the highest number of 2,093 contributions in the repository and ranks first among all central universities in North East India.

Roy & Ghosh (2022) have made a study of the contribution of open universities to the Shodhganga repository. Their finding is that during the period of 1985 to 2005, a total of thirteen state open universities and one national open university were established in India. Out of the total contributions of open universities to Shodhganga, 40% are from one national open university and 60% are from nine state level open universities. Faculties of social sciences and humanities account for 90% of the uploaded theses. With respect of the languages of the uploaded theses, the ratio between English and regional languages is 7:3. Hindi, Marathi, Gujarathi and Assamese are the major non-English languages.

The present paper is based on an intensive case study of theses in the domain of Assamese Language and Literature for which Doctorate Degree was awarded from the universities in Assam and have been uploaded in the

Shodhganga. The intention is to identify the research trend over the years.

3. Objectives of the Study

- i. To find the growth of doctoral theses contributed from Assam in the Shodhganga.
- ii. To find out the number of doctoral theses in Assamese Language and Literature in the universities of Assam.
- iii. To find out the year-wise distribution of the theses uploaded in the Shodhganga.
- iv. To find out the page-wise distribution of the theses.
- v. To find out the number of citations in the theses.
- vi. To identify the highly contributed research supervisors.

4. Methodology

The present study covers data about the 445 doctoral theses available in Shodhganga from the Department of Assamese, in the universities of the state of Assam, as of November 2022. The bibliographic data of doctoral theses on Assamese Language and Literature are collected from the Shodhganga, The ETDs of Indian universities by INFLIBNET. It is a major source of bibliometric information of doctoral theses awarded by the various universities in the country as well as in the state of Assam. The collected data are analyzed based on the objectives of the study.

5. Data Analysis

5.1. Status of the theses uploaded in the Shodhganga

The total number of government universities in Assam comprises two central universities and 17 state universities. In addition there are six private universities and one Deemed University in the state. Out of these, 12 universities - 10 state universities and two central universities - have signed MoU with Shodhganga to upload their ETDs. The total number of Ph.D. theses uploaded from these universities in North East India comes to 9397. Table 1 shows the year of establishment and the number of theses uploaded by each of these 12 universities.

Table 1: University-wise distribution of the number of ETDs uploaded in the Shodhganga

Sl. No.	Name of the University	Year of starting	Category	No of theses	Percentage (%)
1	Gauhati University	1948	State	6052	64.40
2	Assam University, Silchar	1994	Central	1900	20.21
3	Tezpur University	1994	Central	728	7.74
4	Dibrugarh University	1965	State	592	6.29
5	Bodoland University	2009	State	70	0.74
6	Mahapurusha Srimanta Sankaradeva Viswavidyalaya	2014	State	25	0.26
7	Krishna Kanta Handiqui State Open University	2006	State	12	0.12
8	National Law University and Judicial Academy, Assam	2009	State	12	0.12
9	Assam Rajiv Gandhi University of Cooperative Management	2010	State	2	0.02
10	Assam Science and Technology University	2010	State	2	0.02
11	Assam Agriculture University	1969	State	1	0.01
12	Cotton University	2017	State	1	0.01
Total				9397	100.00

The major share is from Gauhati University, which is the oldest among the group, with 6052 (64.40%) ETDs and it occupies the first rank. This is followed by the two central universities – Assam University, Silchar contributing 1900 (20.21%) theses and the Tezpur University with 728 (7.74%) theses respectively. Assam Agriculture University and the Cotton University have uploaded only one thesis each as on the date of collecting data for the study.

5.2 Theses on Assamese Language and Literature

Out of the total 9397 theses uploaded to Shodhganga, the share of theses on Assamese Language and Literature comes to 445, which is 4.74% and these are from four universities. Table 2 shows the names of these universities, the total number of ETDs they have uploaded and the share of theses on the subject domain under study. Figure 1 & Table 2 shows the university wise distribution of Assamese language and literature theses in the Shodhganga.

Figure 1: Share of Assamese theses in the Shodhganga.

Being the oldest university in the state, the Gauhati University has the major share with 389 (87.41%) theses and it is followed by Dibrugarh University with 46 (10.33%) theses. Mahapurusha Srimanta Sankaradeva Viswavidyalaya and the Bodoland University have uploaded seven and three theses respectively, in Assamese Language and Literature.

Table 2: University-wise distribution of theses on Assamese language and literature

Sl. No.	Name of the University	Total No. of theses	Theses on Assamese Lang. and Lit.	Percentage (%)	Rank
1	Gauhati University	6052	389	6.43	1
2	Dibrugarh University	592	46	7.77	2
3	Mahapurusha Srimanta Sankaradeva Viswavidyalaya	25	7	28	3
4	Bodoland University	70	3	4.29	4
Total		6739	445	6.6	

5.3 Year-wise Productivity of Ph.Ds.

The Gauhati University which was founded in 1948, is the first university in Assam to award a Ph.D. in the subject area of Assamese Language and Literature and that was in 1958. During the period of 51 years from 1958 to 2009 Doctoral degree in the domain of Assamese language and literature was awarded to a total of 157 scholars. Table 3 which gives an year-wise distribution awarding Ph Ds shows that from 2010 to 2022, Gauhati University has awarded the maximum number (232) Ph.Ds. This is followed by Dibrugarh University with 46 and Bodoland University with 7. The number of Ph Ds awarded by Gauhati University, is the highest (35 nos) in 2017, and this is followed by the year 2018. The two years (2017 and 2018) taken together account for 17.73% of the total. For Dibrugarh University also, 2017 and 2018 are the most productive years, contributing more than 67% of the total theses produced by the university in the domain of Assamese Language and Literature.

Table 3: Year- wise Distribution of awarding Ph.Ds.

Sl. No.	Year of Awarding Ph.D.	Gauhati University	Dibrugarh University	Mahapurusha Srimanta Sankaradeva Viswavidyalaya	Bodoland University
1	1958 to 2009	157(40.35%)	0	0	0
2	2010	9(2.31%)	1(2.17%)	0	0
3	2011	16(4.11%)	0	0	0
4	2012	12(3.08%)	0	0	0
5	2013	16(4.11%)	0	0	0
6	2014	18(4.62%)	0	0	0
7	2015	13(3.34%)	1(2.17%)	0	0
8	2016	26(6.68%)	1(2.17%)	0	0
9	2017	35(8.99%)	17(36.95%)	0	0
10	2018	34(8.74%)	14(30.43%)	0	0
11	2019	29(7.45%)	11(23.91%)	2(66.66%)	0
12	2020	17(4.37%)	1(2.17%)	0	4(57.14%)
13	2021	7(1.79%)	0	1(33.33%)	2(28.57%)
14	2022	0	0	0	1(14.28%)
Total		389	46	3	7

5.4 Uploading Theses to Shodhganga

Table 4 gives an year-wise statistics of uploading Ph D theses in Assamese Language and Literature by the four Universities in the state. It is found that the highest number of 237(60.92%) theses were uploaded by Gauhati University in 2016, followed by 24(52.17%) theses by Dibrugarh University in the year 2021. Gauhati University uploaded the lowest 1(0.25%) thesis in the year 2014 and 2015, and only one thesis was uploaded by Dibrugarh University in the year 2018 and 2019.

5.5 Top-Ranked Research Guides

Table 5 gives a ranked list of 25 research

guides in the domain of Assamese Language and Literature and their parent Universities. It is found that the top four research guides belong to the Gauhati University and they together account for 69 Ph Ds. Umesh Deka, who is ranked as first, has 24 Ph.Ds. The second in the list, Dipti Phukan Patgiri has supervised 17 Ph.Ds during the period of the study. It is also found that Nava Kumar Handique is the most productive research guide in Dibrugarh University, while Deka Hazarika, Karabi the most productive research guide in the Mahapurusha Srimanta Sankaradeva Viswavidyalaya. Both of them have seven theses each to their credit.

Table 4: University-wise Distribution of Theses

Sl. No.	Year of Ph.D. Theses Uploaded	Gauhati University (%)	Dibrugarh University (%)	Mahapurusha Srimanta Sankaradeva Viswavidyalaya (%)	Bodoland University (%)
1	2014	1(0.25%)	0	0	0
2	2015	1(0.25%)	0	0	0
3	2016	237(60.92%)	0	0	0
4	2017	11(2.82%)	0	0	0
5	2018	25(6.42%)	1(2.17%)	0	0
6	2019	40(10.28%)	1(2.17%)	0	0
7	2020	37(9.51%)	6(13.04%)	-0	2 (66.66%)
8	2021	21(5.39%)	24(52.17%)	6 (85.71%)	1 (33.33%)
9	2022	16(4.11%)	14(20.43%)	1 (14.28%)	0 (%)
	Total	389	46	7	3

Table 5: Distribution of Top-ranked Research Supervisors

Sl.No.	Supervisors	Affiliation	Number of Ph.D. Theses
1	Deka, Umesh	Gauhati University	24
2	Patgiri, Dipti Phukan	Gauhati University	17
3	Bora, Lilabati Saikia	Gauhati University	14
4	Rajbongshi, Paramananda	Gauhati University	14
5	Konwar, Arpana	Dibrugarh University	13
6	Baruah, Bijoya	Gauhati University	10
7	Bharali, Bibha	Gauhati University	10
8	Bharali, Sailen	Gauhati University	10
9	Goswami, Malinee	Gauhati University	10
10	Mahanta, Pradip Jyoti	Gauhati University	10
11	Nath, Prafulla Kumar	Gauhati University	10
12	Neog, Maheswar	Gauhati University	10

13	Thakur, Nagen	Gauhati University	10
14	Pathak, Ramesh	Gauhati University	9
15	Saharia, Kanak Chandra	Gauhati University	9
16	Hakacham, Upen Rabha	Gauhati University	8
17	Sarma, Banikanta	Gauhati University	8
18	Sarma, Satyendra Nath	Gauhati University	8
19	Bhattacharya, Parag Kumar	Gauhati University	7
20	Goswami, Satyandra Narayan	Gauhati University	7
21	Mazumdar, Bimal	Gauhati University	7
22	Sarma, Nabin Chandra	Gauhati University	7
23	Handique, Nava Kumar	Dibrugarh University	7
24	Deka, Hazarika Karabi	Mahapurusha Srimanta Sankaradeva Viswavidyalaya	7
25	Ahmed, Kamaluddin	Gauhati University	6

5.6 Distribution of References

The investigators have made an attempt to make a quantitative analysis of the number of references attached to the theses under study. The 445 theses together have 60237 references listed, the average number comes to 135 per thesis. The number of references in a thesis is in the range of 36 to 450. Table 6 gives a frequency distribution of the attached references. The average number of references per thesis comes to 144.23 for Gauhati University, 143 for Dibrugarh University, 160 for Bodoland University and 106 for Mahapurusha Srimanta Sankaradeva Viswavidyalaya. The highest number of references is in the range of 101-200, and it is consistently so for all the four universities under consideration.

5.7 Length of Theses

Attempt was also made to examine size of the theses in terms of the total number of pages. Table 7 shows the distribution of the theses with respect to the number of pages as obtained from the Shodhganga portal. The number of pages ranges from less than 150 to more than 851. The modal value of the number of pages is found to be in the range 250 to 300; there are 156 theses in this group. It is found that the size of 287 theses is in the range of 201 to 300 pages. The theses with the smallest and largest number of pages in this group were actually emanated from the Gauhati University. The 46 theses from the Dibrugarh University are of 151 to 400 pages; of these 25 have a size of 201 to 300 pages.

Table 6 : Distribution of References

No. of references	Gauhati University	Dibrugarh University	Mahapurusha Srimanta Sankaradeva Viswavidyalaya	Bodoland University	Total
1-100	14293(27.37%)	776(11.79%)	36(11.28%)	0	15,105
101-200	27182(52.05%)	3710(56.37%)	283(88.71%)	871(77.76%)	32,046
200-300	9691(18.55%)	1645(24.99%)	0	249(22.23%)	11,585
301-400	1051(2.01%)	0	0	0	1,051
401-500	0	450(6.83%)	0	0	450
Total	52,217	6581	319	1120	60237

Table 7 : Length of Theses

Number of Pages	Gauhati University	Dibrugarh University	Mahapurusha Srimanta Sankaradeva Viswavidyalaya	Bodoland University	Total
001-150	5(1.28%)	0	0	0	5
151-200	42(10.79%)	8(17.39%)	1(33.33%)	2(28.57%)	53
201-250	114(29.30%)	13(28.26%)	2(66.66%)	2(28.57%)	131
251-300	141(36.24%)	12(26.08%)	0	3(42.85%)	156
301-350	45(11.56%)	9(19.56%)	0	0	54
351-400	14(3.59%)	4(8.69%)	0	0	18
401-450	15(3.85%)	0	0	0	15
451-500	6(1.54%)	0	0	0	6
501-550	2(0.51%)	0	0	0	2
551-600	1(0.25%)	0	0	0	1
601-650	1(0.25%)	0	0	0	1
651-700	0	0	0	0	0
701-750	1(0.25%)	0	0	0	1
751-800	1(0.25%)	0	0	0	1
801-850	0	0	0	0	0
851-900	1(0.25%)	0	0	0	1
Total	389(100.00)	46(100.00)	3(100.00)	7(100.00)	445

6. Findings of the Study

The major findings of the study are summarised below.

- There are 9397 Ph.D. theses uploaded from North East India, Gauhati University occupies the first rank in terms of contributing the highest number of ETDs in Shodhganga.
- A total of 445 Doctoral theses were generated in the domain of Assamese Language and Literature from the four universities, out of which Gauhati University contributed the highest number (389) which comes to 87.42% of the total.
- Gauhati University awarded the highest number of theses in 2017, with 35(8.99%) Ph.D., followed by Dibrugarh University with 17(36.95%) Ph.D. in the same year.
- The highest number of 237(60.92%) theses were uploaded by Gauhati University in 2016, followed by 24(52.17%) theses uploaded by Dibrugarh University in 2021.
- Deka, Umesh, and Patgiri, Dipti Phukan, both from Gauhati University, are identified as research guides who supervised 24 and 17 Ph.Ds. Respectively.
- The maximum number of theses have a size in the range of 251-300 pages, and more than 90% of theses in this group are from the Gauhati University.
- The number of references contained in the theses varies from 36 to 450.
- Almost 87% of the references in the theses appear in the the theses from Gauhati University, which accounts for 87.4% of the doctoral theses covered in the study.

7. Conclusion

Electronic Theses and Dissertations (ETDs) form an important resource for research in academic institutions. It helps researchers to know about the research works done in recent years. In this study, it has been observed that the universities of Assam contributed 9397 Ph.D. theses. It is found that the share of theses in the Assamese language is 4.74% (445) of the total theses awarded from all the universities in the state of Assam. The study found that Gauhati University uploaded the highest number of 237(60.92%) theses in 2016, and 35(8.99%) theses were awarded in 2017.

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